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Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Firms' Financial Performance: A Study of Indian Banking Industry

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Abstract

Plethora of researches has been undertaken to determine impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on financial performance (FP) of enterprises, and leads vary extensively. The main reason for such diverse results may be due to flawed evaluation or due to trivial measured variables looked at. In this paper we aim at exploring the partnership between CSR and FP in the Indian financial sector. Data have been gathered from 39 banks listed on BSE for period of 5 years (2015-2019). The result indicates positive impact of CSR on financial performance of banks.

Keywords: Corporate social Responsibility, Financial Performance, Banks.

Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an old concept followed in various ways across the globe from ancient times has gained new momentum in recent decades. Kautilya strongly believed that economic prosperity without any sort of ethical anchoring was not sustainable as well as today CSR is actually surfacing gradually and also acquiring its acceptance via enterprises across the globe (Shamasastri, 1915).

Businesses cannot grow in isolation, for its functioning, they require people and is believed that it is not possible for any business to succeed without the support of the immediate society and other stakeholders. Morrell Heald defined CSR as “recognition on the part of management of an obligation to the society it serves not only for maximum economic performance but for humane and constructive social policies as well (Heald, 1957)”. Bowen defined (SR) as “the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of action which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society (Bowen, 1953)”.

Companies concerns over social contents have increased over the years and companies have understood their role towards the society besides being consistent with objective for earning profit. In recent times there has been increase in researches by academicians to access if there exists any relations between their CSR spending and their performance. There has been mixed results on the studies done by researchers, there are some studies which asserts that expenditure on CSR

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enhances FP of firms (Margolis, Elfenbein, & Walsh, 2009), there are some studies which feel that spending on CSR activities merely effects the profit of firm as it involves cost associated with it (Friedman, 1970).

Corporations' social responsibility has become the most popular and worldwide demand or trend in all business sectors. Banks from all over the world are endorsing the educational, health initiatives, cultural, economic, by recognizing corporate social responsibilities. Corporate social responsibilities differ from place to place, time to time, and from industry to industry (Richard Welford et al., 2007)

The CSR activities in India are increasing day by day that is witnessed that India is making progress concerning the development of socially responsible practices. There is one another significant area is in their scope that involves the different kinds of practices such as strategies for the protection of the environment, activities for the welfare and development of children, and the welfare of the community.

The leading banks of India are introducing a wide spectrum of different kinds of strategies and practices, including the development of rural areas, family initiatives, social walkers and development of the community, empowerment of women and family initiatives.

A meaningful amount from the annual earning of the banks is spent in the social activities, for instance, to support the different structures, individuals from different areas, events, on the education and child healthcare, beautification of the environment, entertainment, development of human capital and art. But it has been reported that the primary focus of the banks is on social welfare.

Review of Literature

The relationship between a company's profitability and its CSR is a very important subject of research. Corporate social responsibility describes a firm's obligation to protect and improve social welfare now as well as in the future, by generating sustainable benefits for stakeholders (Hay et al, 1976).

The theoretical frameworks in which the relationship between CSR and company's profitability can be underpinned are basically two differentiating characteristics. The casual sequence of dependent variables and the positive, negative or neutral sign of the correlation (Preston and O'Bannon, 1997). A total of seven possible types of CSR-FP (Financial Performance) correlations were identified by Preston & O'Bannon (1997) and Waddock & Graves (1997). Beurden and Gossliing (2008) found that out of the seven, most empirical outcomes support the social impact hypothesis and reject all if any negative relationship between CSR and company's business performance.

Researchers and economists have disagreed on the positive relationship between CSR and FP and some say that CSR puts an organization in an economic disadvantage compared to companies who are not as much socially responsible (Ulman 1985, Vance 1975). The disadvantage is caused by the additional costs which stem from programs like employee welfare plans, charities, maintenance of different plants, community development and upgrading to environmentally

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friendly policies (McGuire et al 1988). However, many other studies have found no correlation between CSR and company's performance (Guerard et al 1988, Alexander & Buchholz 1978). Freeman 1984 theorised that higher level of CSR practices eventually lead to better business performance and named it the stakeholder theory. This theory states that the success of a firm is directly proportional to the company's capability to manage good relationships with the stakeholders. This management of relationship between the company and its stakeholders is an essential tool to generate value and therefore the interpretation of this theory by different companies in different ways can affect the possible correlation between CSR and company's performance (Hammann et al 2009, Perrini et al 2011)

The need for studying the relationship between CSR and CFP is because there is a major scarcity of studies focusing on explicit CSR activities declared by firms. The studies which have been done have shown mostly mixed results and there is a sever scarcity of such research in Indian context.

Bragdon and Marlin (1972); Vance (1975) found that there is a negative correlation between CSR and CFP, Abbott and Monsen (1979); Alexander and Buchholz (1978) found no definite relationship between the two properties.

However, many other studies in various countries have also shown results where positive relationship between CSR and financial performance has been seen (Bragdon and Marlin (1972); Davis and Blomstrom (1975); Godfrey (2004); Heinz (1976); Jain et al. (2016); McWilliams and Siegel (2001); Moskowitz (1972); Parket and Eilbirt (1975); Soloman and Hansen (1985); Sturdivant and Ginter (1977)). It should be mentioned that when model is properly specified, CSR does not have positive impact on short-term financial performance, it does offer a remarkable long-term fiscal advantage. (Chin-Huang Lin, 2009).

Objective

The study intents to examine the relationship between the CSR and Financial Performance of the selected banks in India.

Hypotheses

H1: CSR is positively associated with Total Assets

H2: CSR is positively associated with Net Profit

Methodology

Data for the present study has been collected from secondary sources for thirty-nine (39) banks for over a period of 5 years (2015-2019) which were listed on BSE during the period of study. The CSR expenditure of each banks are extracted and calculated from the annual reports, sustainability reports of each banks. Further, other secondary sources has been referred to, for gaining access to the data related to financial parameters such as the Net profit and Total Assets, which are used in the present study. Correlation method is used to find the relationship between CSR and financial performance of the firm.

Analysis and Finding

In this study we have tried to see the impact and the relation between the CSR spending of banks operating in India and their financial performance.

Figure 1: Correlation between CSR Spending and Total Assets

Source: Authors own Elaboration

Figure 1 depicts year wise relationship between CSR spending and the total assets of the banks operating in the country. The trend shows a decreasing but positive correlation between the two variables considered for the study. There is a strong positive relationship between CSR and Total Assets for the year 2015 and 2016, and moderate positive relationship for the year 2018 and 2019 whereas there exists a weak positive relationship for the financial year 2019. This shows that spending on corporate social responsibility by banks has positive relation with the total assets of the banks.

Figure 2 depicts the relationship between spending on CSR and the Net Profit of the banks operating in the country. There is found to be strong positive relationship between the spending of CSR and the net profit of the banks for the financial year 2015,2016 and 2017 whereas there exists a moderate positive relationship in the financial year 2018 and 2019 which shows that banks spending on CSR is linked with the net profit.

Figure 2: Correlation between CSR Spending and Net Profit

Source: Authors own Elaboration

Table 1: Overall correlation between CSR Spending and Net Profit and Total Assets

Years	Net Profit	Total Assets
2015	0.947829	0.641378
2016	0.869441	0.622252
2017	0.866667	0.504749
2018	0.638531	0.497474
2019	0.748702	0.440921
overall	0.732305	0.48686

Source: Author own calculation

Table 1 highlights the exact year wise as well as overall correlation between the CSR spending of the banks and the Net Profit and Total assets. The overall result shows that there exists a strong positive correlation between CSR spending and Net Profit of the banking industry over the last five financial years. Likewise there is a moderate positive relationship between Total Assets and the CSR expenses of banking industry, which allows us to understand the existence of positive relationship between the variables taken for the study.

Concluding remarks

The topic of CSR and firm's financial performance has gained a lot of interest from researchers across the globe and plethora of research has been undertaken across various sectors in various parts of the world. With the help of this paper we have tried to understand if there is any relationship between CSR and FP of banking sector in India. For the study we took CSR Spending by banks, their Total Assets and Net profit for the period of five (5) years i.e. financial year 2014-2015 to 2018-2019. The result shows that there is a positive relation between the variables considered for the present study. There exist a strong positive relationship between CSR spending and Net Profit and there is a moderate positive relationship between CSR spending of banks and Total Assets of Banks. The banks in general understand their responsibility towards the society and with the mandate of Companies Act, 2013, the banks are progressive towards spending parts of their profit for social wellbeing.

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Annexures:

Table 1: Net Profit of Banks

NET Profit (in Cr.)						
Sr. No	Name of the Bank	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	Allahabad Bank	620.9	-743.31	-313.51	-4674.37	-8333.96
2	Andhra Bank	638.44	539.84	174.34	-3412.53	-2786.13
3	Bank of Baroda	3398.43	-5395.55	1383.13	-2431.81	433.52
4	Bank of India	1708.92	-6089.22	-1558.34	-6043.71	-5546.9
5	Bank of Maharashtra	450.69	100.69	-1372.51	-1145.65	-4783.88
6	Canara Bank	2702.63	-2812.82	1121.92	-4222.24	347.02
7	Central Bank of India	606.45	-1418.19	-2439.1	-5104.91	-5641.48
8	Corporation Bank	584.26	-506.48	561.21	-4053.94	-6332.98
9	Indian Bank	1005.17	711.38	1405.68	1258.99	321.95
10	Indian Overseas Bank	-454.34	-2897.33	-3416.74	-6299.49	-3737.88
11	Oriental Bank of Commerce	497.08	156.08	-1094.07	-5871.74	54.99
12	Punjab & Sind Bank	121.35	335.97	201.08	-743.8	-543.48
13	Punjab National Bank	3061.58	-3974.39	1324.8	-12282.82	-9975.49
14	State Bank of India	13101.57	9950.65	10484.1	-6547.45	862.23
15	Syndicate Bank	1522.93	-1643.49	358.95	-3222.84	-2588.3
16	UCO Bank	1137.8	-2799.25	-1850.67	-4436.37	-4321.1
17	Union Bank of India	1781.64	1351.6	555.23	-5247.37	-2947.45
18	United Bank of India	255.99	-281.96	219.51	-1454.44	-2315.92

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19	Axis Bank Ltd.	7,357.82	8,223.66	3,679.28	275.68	4,676.61
20	Bandhan Bank Ltd.	0.58	275.25	1111.95	1,345.56	1,951.50
21	Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	-53.17	-149.72	1.55	-97.47	-197.42
22	City Union Bank Ltd.	395.02	444.69	502.77	592	682.85
23	DCB Bank Ltd.	191.18	194.52	199.68	245.34	325.37
24	Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd.	-241.47	-209.45	12.38	-24.87	11.66
25	Federal Bank Ltd.	1,005.75	475.65	830.79	878.85	1,243.89
26	HDFC Bank Ltd	10,215.92	12,296.23	14,549.66	17,486.75	21,078.14
27	ICICI Bank Ltd.	11,175.35	9,726.29	9,801.09	6,777.42	3363.3
28	IndusInd Bank Ltd	1,793.72	2,286.45	2,867.89	3,605.99	3,301.10
29	IDFC Bank Ltd.	2.58	466.85	1,019.74	859.3	-1,944.18
30	Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	508.6	416.04	-1,632.29	202.72	464.89
31	Karnataka Bank Ltd.	451.45	415.29	452.26	325.61	477.24
32	Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	464.28	567.63	605.98	345.67	210.87
33	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd	1,865.98	2,089.78	3,411.50	4,084.30	4,865.33
34	Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	132.29	180.24	256.07	-584.87	-894.1
35	Nainital bank Ltd.	67.18	46.97	48.46	48.88	26.88
36	RBL Bank Ltd.	207.17	292.48	446.05	635.09	866.95
37	South Indian Bank Ltd.	307.2	333.27	392.5	334.89	247.53
38	YES Bank Ltd.	2,005.36	2,539.45	3,330.09	4,224.56	1,720.27
39	IDBI Bank Limited	873.39	-3,664.80	-5,158.14	-8,237.93	-15,116.30

Source: Annual Reports of Banks

Table 2: Total Assets of Banks

Total Assets (in Cr.)						
Sr. No	Name of the Bank	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	Allahabad Bank	227679.66	240457.21	237962.63	253717.69	249576.66
2	Andhra Bank	185170.35	199961.76	222126.12	242171.37	249311.42
3	Bank of Baroda	714988.55	671376.48	694875.42	719999.8	780987.4
4	Bank of India	618697.75	609913.92	626309.26	609574.82	625222.84
5	Bank of Maharashtra	146018.79	160957.32	159323.98	156328.75	164535.53
6	Canara Bank	548000.56	552960.78	583519.44	616886.1	694766.69
7	Central Bank of India	311940.5	305466.1	333401.94	326225.27	330717.66
8	Corporation Bank	225993.01	234863.61	247891.05	221891.31	213577.85
9	Indian Bank	192835.97	203710.38	218233.14	252715.82	280065.27
10	Indian Overseas Bank	285636.98	274436.76	247167.48	247968.03	250008.36
11	Oriental Bank of Commerce	230513.57	239768	253064.72	233344.04	271909.56
12	Punjab & Sind Bank	97753.4	102581.42	96643.44	113759.24	108982.05
13	Punjab National Bank	603333.6	667390.46	720330.55	765830.1	774949.46
14	State Bank of India	2048079.79	2357617.53	2705966.3	3454751.99	3680914.24
15	Syndicate Bank	303135.25	307967.44	299073.33	323977.13	311278.86
16	UCO Bank	245916.9	244882.53	231339.7	216056.17	230484.08
17	Union Bank of India	381615.93	404695.9	452704.44	487380.08	494038.84
18	United Bank of India	123027.57	129431.75	141053.11	144748.65	151529.92

19	Axis Bank Ltd.	4,61,932.39	5,25,467.62	6,01,467.67	6,91,329.58	8,00,996.53
20	Bandhan Bank Ltd.	526.89	19,756.50	30,236.09	44,310.06	56,441.71
21	Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	15762.27	15651.94	16223.24	15870.05	16911.16
22	City Union Bank Ltd.	27871.12	31803.96	35270.77	39937.24	45258.88
23	DCB Bank Ltd.	16132.3	19,118.52	24,046.38	30,222.09	35,791.83
24	Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd.	14351.9	12462.98	12333.12	12286.45	11798.88
25	Federal Bank Ltd.	82850.48	94581.37	114976.93	138313.95	159339.99
26	HDFC Bank Ltd	5,90,503.08	7,08,845.57	8,63,840.21	10,63,934.31	12,44,540.71
27	ICICI Bank Ltd.	6,46,129.29	7,20,695.10	7,71,791.45	879189.16	964459.15
28	IndusInd Bank Ltd	109115.91	142896.99	178648.41	221626.16	277819.41
29	IDFC Bank Ltd.	0.05	83215.87	112159.65	126520.17	167184.86
30	Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	76085.45	80268.07	82018.67	89687.61	101406.28
31	Karnataka Bank Ltd.	51836.6	56500.33	64126.55	70373.68	79045.76
32	Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	53152.47	58984.71	61807.62	66941.43	69340.11
33	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd	1,06,012.08	1,92,259.79	2,14,589.96	2,64,933.39	3,12,172.09
34	Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	24705.43	28670.48	35244.72	40429.22	33046.16
35	Nainital bank Ltd.	5977.92	6084.39	7699.68	8114.68	8101.75
36	RBL Bank Ltd.	27,104.67	39,161.08	48,674.77	61,850.75	80,358.82
37	South Indian Bank Ltd.	59,116.32	63,474.88	74,312.15	82685.87	92279.22
38	YES Bank Ltd.	136170.4	165263.41	215059.91	312445.6	380826.16
39	IDBI Bank Limited	3,56,030.56	3,75,389.82	3,61,767.90	3,50,085.72	3,20,284.49

Source: Annual Reports of Banks

Table 3: CSR Spending of Banks

CSR Spending (in Cr.)						
Sr. No	Name of the Bank	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	Allahabad Bank	8.54	10.99	8.27	6.45	9.22
2	Andhra Bank	1.06	1.28	3.19	1.49	0
3	Bank of Baroda	17.83	19.4	0	11.91	0.05
4	Bank of India	11.85	0	6.42	2.18	3.95
5	Bank of Maharashtra	0	0	0.29	0	0
6	Canara Bank	30.4	0	32.68	28.53	23.62
7	Central Bank of India	0	6.06	0	0	0
8	Corporation Bank	0.25	0.22	2.06	3.24	3.72
9	Indian Bank	1.18	2.96	2.65	5.72	2.42
10	Indian Overseas Bank	0.27	0.28	0	0	0
11	Oriental Bank of Commerce	2	0	1.23	0.05	0.05
12	Punjab & Sind Bank	0	0	0.74	1.39	0
13	Punjab National Bank	3.75	6.76	2.73	28.61	29.54
14	State Bank of India	115.8	143.92	109.82	112.96	48.81
15	Syndicate Bank	2.14	12.93	1.45	1.4	0.48
16	UCO Bank	1.7	4.23	20.85	10.41	8.18
17	Union Bank of India	13.25	6.98	7.27	5.55	0.45
18	United Bank of India	0.63	0.21	0.57	0	0

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19	Axis Bank Ltd.	123.22	137.41	135.39	133.77	137.59
20	Bandhan Bank Ltd.	0	0.05	4.21	14.14	27.83
21	Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	0.06	0.003	0	0	0
22	City Union Bank Ltd.	3.54	8.05	8.16	9.7	9.35
23	DCB Bank Ltd.	0	1.01	0.98	1.77	3.87
24	Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd.	0	0	0	0	0
25	Federal Bank Ltd.	7.27	12.3	15.42	14.01	17.04
26	HDFC Bank Ltd	118.55	194.81	305.42	374	443.8
27	ICICI Bank Ltd.	156	172	182	170.38	92.2
28	IndusInd Bank Ltd	17.54	27.32	33.81	20.47	55.46
29	IDFC Bank Ltd.	0	23.4	4.85	14.23	20.82
30	Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	13.74	28.48	21.87	31.71	12.46
31	Karnataka Bank Ltd.	2.04	6.06	6.56	8.19	8.7
32	Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	1.14	2.05	1.6	3.7	7.09
33	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd	11.97	16.41	17.33	26.4	36.55
34	Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	0.12	0.87	1.4	0.61	0.29
35	Nainital bank Ltd.	0	0.26	0.27	0.1	0.1
36	RBL Bank Ltd.	1.61	1.6	3.68	6.95	10.55
37	South Indian Bank Ltd.	1.46	2.3	4.03	7.28	12.22
38	YES Bank Ltd.	15.71	29.52	41.66	45.21	53.78
39	IDBI Bank Limited	23.44	9.44	4.35	1.36	0.25

Source: Annual Reports of Banks